

The Flow Experience in Leisure among Undergraduates And its Influencing Factors

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ABSTRACT: Leisure is a survival or life state of cultural creation, cultural appreciation and cultural construction, which is caused by people's leisure and in order to continuously meet people's various needs. It creates cultural atmosphere, transmits cultural information and constructs cultural artistic conception through the common behaviors, thoughts and feelings of human groups, so as to achieve the comprehensive and complete development of individual body, mind and will. The aim of this study is to explore the status of leisure and flow experience in leisure, and analyze the influencing factors of leisure flow experience among undergraduates. Seven hundred and eighty-seven undergraduates (377 males and 410 females) are selected by stratified random sampling from 7 universities in Guangdong Province. They are investigated with Leisure Flow Experience Questionnaire (LFEQ) and a self-compiled questionnaire on personal general information of leisure. The survey results indicate the following three points. First, 51.92% of college students have more than 4 hours of leisure time per day on average. College students' leisure activities are mainly static, entertainment and simple rest. Second, the total scores of LFEQ is (161.73 ± 19.81) .

Third, There is significant difference in the percentage of college students who have experienced and have not experienced fluency experience in various leisure activities ($\chi^2=80.613$, $P < .001$). Final, the results of multiple stepwise linear regression analysis show that the total score of LFEQ is positively related to the following 8 factors like family economic status, academic performance, only child or not, mother's occupation, leisure time length during weekdays, liking exploratory tourism at leisure, major category, and college category ($\beta = 0.091, 0.120, 0.109, 0.096, 0.086, 0.074, 0.073, 0.069$, all $P < 0.05$), while father's occupation, gender and like strolling at leisure are negatively related to the total score of LFEQ ($\beta = -0.139, 0.134, -0.080$, all $P < 0.05$). **Conclusion** College students have plenty of leisure time, and the leisure activities and leisure flow experience need to be improved. The characteristics of leisure activities, gender and family factors (such as family economic status and parents' occupations) may be the relevant factors of college students' leisure flow experience.

KeyWords: Undergraduates, Leisure, Flow Experience in Leisure, Influencing Factors

I. Introduction

There is no unified definition of leisure. The most recognized is the definition given by Jeffrey Goby [1]: "Leisure is a relatively free life freed from the external stress of the cultural and material environment. It enables individuals to act in the way they like and instinctively feel valuable, driven by their inner love, and provides a basis for faith." That is to say, leisure is free and voluntary to do some new things, Create some new realities and realize new development. It is a process to meet the needs of physical and mental development, so leisure is also an inner experience, and a way of life. Scientific and civilized leisure can provide people with opportunities for recreation, relaxation and entertainment, and can effectively promote the saving and release of energy, including the regulation of intelligence and physical energy and the exercise of physiological and psychological functions, meet psychological needs such as self-improvement and self-confidence [2], promote psychosomatic health [3-4], and enhance subjective well-being [5].

The concept "flow experience" was first proposed by Csikszentmihalyi, also known as optimal experience. It refers to a kind of overall feeling that people feel when they are fully engaged in activities. It shows that the people are completely attracted by the activities, the consciousness is concentrated in an unusually narrow range, and the perception and ideas irrelevant to the activities are filtered out, and they lose self-consciousness and enter the realm of selflessness. At that time, people only respond to specific and explicit feedback, and obtain a sense of whole-body penetration, while generating a sense of control through manipulating the environment. The difference between self stimulation and reaction, between self and environment, and between the past, present and future is very small [6]. This is a temporary, subjective and pleasant experience, which originates from the activity process itself. The role of external rewards is minimal or non-existent. It comes in a continuous and effortless way, allowing people to carry out these activities without tiring [7], thus helping to improve the quality of life and improve subjective well-being. Csikszentmihalyi believes that in all kinds of active and serious activities (such as sports, learning, puzzle games and so on), people may experience this kind of addictive experience [6].

With the continuous improvement of living conditions, leisure time is increasing, and the significance of leisure is increasingly prominent. Half of the time of college students every year is free time. As the "most leisure group", college students' leisure activities are increasingly rich, but there are more and more problems related to leisure, such as doing nothing all day, blindly pursuing stimulation, lack of self-pursuit, and taking part in inappropriate leisure activities, resulting in various problems, affecting the mental health of college students [8-9], or leisure time and arrangements are at random, or the leisure interest is too narrow and the leisure mode is too simple [10]. The above phenomenon shows that the quality of leisure is not high and college students lack the flow experience of leisure [8, 11]. Therefore, it is of great significance to understand the current situation of college students' leisure activities and leisure flow experience, and clarify the relevant factors of leisure flow experience among college students, so as to do a good job of leisure education and promote college students' healthy growth.

II. Objects and Methods

2.1 Objects

The stratified random sampling method was used to select 831 students from 7 universities (undergraduate first and second batch, Category A) in Guangdong Province. The specific steps are as follows: First, the universities (undergraduate first and second batch, Category A) in Guangdong Province are divided into 7 categories according to the professional category, including science and engineering, liberal arts, agronomy, medicine, sports, arts and comprehensive. Second, one university is randomly selected from each category above, which are respectively South China University of Technology, Guangdong Universities of Foreign Studies, Zhongkai University of Agriculture and Engineering, Guangdong Medical University, Guangzhou Sport University, Xinghai Conservatory of Music, Shenzhen University. Third, the sample size to be drawn is determined according to the proportion of enrollment, which are 150, 147, 62, 123, 118, 50 and 181 respectively. A total of 831 questionnaires are distributed and 787 valid questionnaires are recovered, with an effective rate of 94.7%. There are 377 males and 410 females; 155 in science and engineering, 132 in liberal arts, 62 in agriculture, 114 in medicine, 93 in sports, 50 in art and 181 in management. 213 freshmen, 198 sophomores, 164 juniors, 139 seniors and 73 fifth-year students.

2.2 Tools

2.2.1 Leisure Flow Experience Questionnaire (LFEQ) [12]

Compiled by Zhaoyuan Guo (2003), LFEQ has a total of 45 items which are divided into 9 dimensions: balance between challenge and skill (BCS), unity of knowledge and action (UKA), clear goals (CG), clear feedback (CF), concentration (CN), sense of control (SC), loss of self-consciousness (LSC), sense of loss time (SLT), and self-achieving goals (SAG). The Likert 5-point scoring method is used to score from 1 to 5 points corresponding to “completely disagreed” to “completely agreed.” The higher the score, the stronger the sense of flow experience in leisure. A total score of 180 or more means that individuals have leisure flow experience. In this study, the Cronbach’ α coefficient of the total table is 0.901, and the Cronbach’ α coefficients of the nine dimensions are 0.814 to 0.866.

2.2.2 Self-complied General Personal Information Questionnaire

The questionnaire contains 32 items, such as: gender, grade, school type, professional category, academic performance, origin, only-child or not, major leisure activities, family economic status, father’s occupation, mother’s occupation, father’s education, mother’s education, value of leisure activities, leisure time per day on weekdays, leisure time per day on weekends, etc.

2.3 Data Processing

SPSS 20.0 is used for statistical analysis. Descriptive statistics are used to calculate the mean scores and standard deviations; Pearson product difference correlation is used to explore the correlation among variables; Multiple stepwise linear regression analysis is used to analyze the influencing factors of the total score of LFEQ.

III. Results

3.1 The current situation of college students' leisure

3.1.1 Current situation of leisure time and activities

59.47% of college students think that leisure activities are very important, 32.53% think it is more important, 7.24% think it doesn't matter, 0.64% think it is not important, 0.12% think it is not important; 17.41% of students have less than 2 hours of leisure time per day, 45.74% have 2 to 4 hours of leisure time per day, 24.65% have 4 to 6 hours of leisure time per day, 4.83% have 6 to 8 hours of leisure time per day, and 7.37% have more than 8 hours of leisure time per day; At weekends, 3.68% of students take less than 2 hours of leisure every day, 6.74% of students take 2 to 4 hours of leisure every day, 23.63% of students take 4 to 6 hours of leisure every day, 26.94% of students take 6 to 8 hours of leisure every day, and 39.01% of students take more than 8 hours of leisure every day. 35.58% of students take reading newspapers, magazines and extracurricular books as leisure activities, 77.13% take surfing the Internet as leisure activities, 4.57% take listening to radio as leisure activities, 0.64% take strolling as leisure activities, 33.29% of students take self-study as leisure activities, 42.06% take chatting with friends as leisure activities, 48.54% take watching movies and listening to music as leisure activities, 69.76% take playing computer games as leisure activities, 24.78% of students take sports as their leisure activities, 22.49% take playing cards and chess as their leisure activities, 3.81% take social part-time jobs as their leisure activities, 16.90% take exploratory tourism as their leisure activities, 13.09% take activities of school clubs as their leisure activities, 11.94% take talent learning as their leisure activities, 32.27% take sleeping as their leisure activities, and 6.69% take other activities as their leisure activities.

3.1.2 Current situation of flow experience in leisure

It can be seen from Table 1 that the total score of LFEQ is (161.73 ± 19.81) , and the average score of each item is (3.59 ± 0.44) , which is a medium to high score [12].

Table 1 Descriptive statistics of LFEQ scores (n=787)

Dimension	M±SD	Max	Min
BCS	18.83±2.970	25	7
UKA	18.84±2.986	25	9
CG	17.86±2.470	25	7
CF	17.81±2.433	25	9
CN	17.57±2.568	25	8
SC	17.04±2.724	25	7
LSC	15.88±3.063	25	8
SLT	18.37±3.202	25	9
SAG	19.56±3.074	25	8
LFEQ	161.73±19.81	225	91

(2) The results of frequency statistics show that 124 students have a total score of more than 180, accounting for 15.76% (124/787) of the sample. In other words, 84.24% of college students in this group lack leisure flow experience.

(3) Comparison of the percentage of students who have experienced flow in various leisure activities

It can be seen from Table 2 that there are statistical significance among the percentages of college students who have experienced and have not experienced flow experience in various leisure activities ($\chi^2= 80.613$, $P<.001$).

Table 2 difference in Percentages of students with and without leisure flow experience in various leisure activities

Activities	with flow experience	without flow experience	χ^2	<i>P</i>
Sports	102	685	80.613	<.001
Hobbies	120	667		
Puzzle games	82	705		
Audio and visual	115	672		
Social	92	695		
Other activities	22	765		

3.2 Comparison of LFEQ scores of the variables of genders and only child or not

According to Table 3, boys score significantly higher than girls in the total score of LFEQ and the four dimensions of "skills-challenge balance", "clear goal", "clear feedback" and "sense of control" ($t=2.019\sim 3.447$, $P=0.044\sim 0.001$); The total score of the only children in LFEQ and its nine dimensions are significantly higher than those of the non only children ($t=2.276 \sim 4.249$, both $P<0.05$).

Table 3 Comparison of LFEQ scores between boys and girls, between only children and non only children

Dimension	Gender		<i>t</i>	<i>P</i>	Only-children or not		<i>t</i>	<i>P</i>
	Boys	Girls			Yes	No		
	(<i>n</i> =375)	(<i>n</i> =410)			(<i>n</i> =195)	(<i>n</i> =590)		
BCS	19.10±2.83	18.57±3.07	2.510	0.012	19.58±3.02	18.57±2.91	4.136	<
	0	5			5	4		0.001
UKA	19.01±2.94	18.68±3.01	1.514	0.130	19.53±3.00	18.60±2.93	3.830	<
	7	6			6	9		0.001
CG	19.08±2.51	17.66±2.40	2.353	0.009	18.50±2.47	17.65±2.43	4.249	<
	9	9			3	2		0.001
CF	18.01±2.55	16.80±2.29	2.173	0.030	18.31±2.44	17.64±2.40	3.334	0.00
	9	9			3	7		1
CN	17.68±2.70	17.27±2.43	1.149	0.251	17.93±2.64	17.45±2.54	2.276	0.02

	4	6			3	1		3
SC	18.39±2.66	14.72±2.74	3.447	0.001	17.48±2.77	16.90±2.69	2.587	0.01
LSC	4	3	1.073	0.283	2	8	2.448	0
	16.01±3.15	15.77±2.98			16.41±3.66	15.70±2.82		0.01
	0	0			5	5		5
SLT	18.34±3.16	18.40±3.24	-0.31	0.791	18.87±3.28	18.20±3.15	2.546	0.01
	4	0	5		3	4		1
SAG	19.63±2.96	19.50±3.17	0.574	0.566	20.13±3.08	19.36±3.04	3.024	0.00
	2	6			5	9		3
LFEQ	165.25±19.	157.37±19.	2.019	0.024	166.66±21.	160.06±19.	4.065	<
	72	82			03	12		0.001

3.3 Regression analysis of factors influencing leisure flow experience

3.3.1 Regression Analysis

3.3.1 Variable Assignment

The possible situations (alternative answers) of 32 demographic classification variables that may affect the total score of LFEQ are assigned, and the results are shown in Table 4.

Table-4. variable assignments

Items	Options and assignments
1. Gender	0 = Male, 1 = Female
2. Grade	0 = Freshman, 1 = Sophomores , 2 = Juniors, 3 = Seniors, 4= Fifth-year students
3. Academic performance	0 = 70% or below of the grade, 1 = 51 ~ 70% of the grade, 2 = 31 ~ 50% of the grade, 3 = 11 ~ 30% of the grade, 4 = top 10% of the grade
4.School category	0 = Science and Technology, 1 = Liberal Arts, 2 = Agronomy, 3 = Medicine, 4 = Sports, 5 = Art, 6 = General
5. Major category	0 = Science, 1 = Engineering, 2 = Liberal Arts, 3 = Agronomy, 4 = Medicine, 5 = Sports, 6 = Art, 7 = Management
6. only-child or not	0 = Yes, 1 = No
7. Family economic status	0 = Poverty, 1 = Struggle, 2 = Normal, 3 = Well-off, 4 = Rich
8. Origin	0 = City, 1 = Town, 2 = Rural
9. Father's education	0 = Primary school or below, 1 = Junior high school, 2 = High school, 3 = University or above
10. Mother's education	0 = Primary school or below, 1 = Junior high school, 2 = High school,

- 3 = University or above
- 0 = IT and communication, 1 = Finance, Securities and insurance,
2 = Commerce and trade, 3 = Energy, 4 = Journalism, 5 = Real estate, 6
= Tourism,
7 = Manufacturing, 8 = Education, 9 = Other
11. Father's occupation
- 0 = IT and communication, 1 = Finance, securities and insurance,
2 = Commerce and trade, 3 = Energy, 4 = Journalism, 5 = Real estate, 6
= Tourism,
7 = Manufacturing, 8 = Education, 9 = Other
12. Mother's occupation
- 0 = Very important, 1 = More important, 2 = Normal, 3 = Less
important,
4 = Not important
13. The meaning of
leisure
- 0 = Less than 2h, 1 = 2~4h (including 2h), 2 = 4~6h (including 4h),
3 = 6~8h (including 6h), 4 = Above 8h (including 8h)
14. Leisure time length
per day on weekdays
- 0 = Less than 2h, 1 = 2~4h (including 2h), 2 = 4~6h (including 4h),
3 = 6~8h (including 6h), 4 = Above 8h (including 8h)
15. Leisure time length
per day on weekends
- 0 = Dislike, 1 = Like
16. Do you like reading
during leisure?
- 0 = Dislike, 1 = Like
17. Do you like to go
online during leisure?
- 0 = Dislike, 1 = Like
18. Do you like to listen
to the radio during
leisure?
- 0 = Dislike, 1 = Like
19. Do you like to hang
out at leisure?
- 0 = Dislike, 1 = Like
20. Do you like self-study
at leisure?
- 0 = Dislike, 1 = Like
21. Do you like chatting
with friends in your
leisure time?
- 0 = Dislike, 1 = Like
22. Do you like to watch
movies at leisure?
- 0 = Dislike, 1 = Like
23. Do you like to listen
to music at leisure?
- 0 = Dislike, 1 = Like
24. Do you like computer
games at leisure?

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25. Do you like sports in your leisure time? 0 = Dislike, 1 = Like
26. Do you like playing chess and cards in your leisure time? 0 = Dislike, 1 = Like
27. Do you like to work part-time during leisure? 0 = Dislike, 1 = Like
28. Do you like traveling during leisure? 0 = Dislike, 1 = Like
29. Do you like club activities during leisure? 0 = Dislike, 1 = Like
30. Do you like talent activities during leisure? 0 = Dislike, 1 = Like
31. Do you like to sleep lazy during leisure? 0 = Dislike, 1 = Like
32. Do you like other leisure activities? 0 = Dislike, 1 = Like
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3.3.2 Multiple Stepwise Linear Regression Analysis of Factors Related to Flow Experience in Leisure among Undergraduates

Taking the total score of LFEQ as the dependent variable and 32 categorical variables as independent variables, the multiple stepwise linear regression analysis is carried out within 95% confidence interval, and the results are shown in Table 5.

From Table 5, it can be seen that the total score of LFEQ is positively correlated with the following 8 factors like family's financial status, academic performance, only child or not, mother's occupation, Leisure time length per day on weekdays, like exploratory tourism at leisure, major category, school category ($\beta = .069$ to $.120$, all $P < 0.05$), and negatively related with father's occupation, gender and like strolling at leisure ($\beta = -.134$ to $-.363$, $P < .05$).

Table 5 Multiple stepwise linear regression analysis of main influencing factors of LFEQ total score

Dependent variable	Independent variable	B	SE	β	t	P	R^2	R_{adj}^2
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LFEQ	family's financial status	2.468		.091	2.457	.014	.098	.086
		1.004						
	academic performance	2.065	.593	.120	3.483	.001		
	only child or not	4.952	1.590	.109	3.115	.002		
	father's occupation	-.973	.285	-.139	-3.416	.001		
	mother's occupation	.749	.305	.096	2.452	.014		
	like strolling	-3.364	1.456	-.134	-2.310	.021		
	leisure time on weekdays	1.621	.654	.086	2.480	.013		
		5.122	2.394	.074	2.139	.033		
	like exploratory tourism at leisure	-2.448	.498	-.363	-4.580	<.001		
	gender							
	school category	1.546	.273	.069	2.003	.046		
	major category	2.140	.344	.073	6.764	<.001		

IV. Discussion

92.00% of college students have a positive attitude towards leisure; 51.92% of college students have more than 4 hours of leisure every day, 36.85% have more than 4 hours of leisure every day on weekdays, and 89.59% have more than 4 hours of leisure every weekend; Video games, surfing the Internet, watching movies, listening to music, chatting, meeting friends and reading extracurricular books are the main leisure activities of college students. Only 33.29% of the students take self-study as their leisure activities, 24.78% take sports as their leisure activities, 16.90% take tourism as their leisure activities, 13.09% take activities of school associations as their leisure activities, 11.94% take talent learning as their leisure activities, and 32.27% take sleeping in as their leisure activities, 3.81% take social part-time jobs as leisure activities, which is consistent with the results of previous studies [13-15], suggesting that current college students generally attach importance to and are willing to participate in leisure activities, and their leisure time is relatively abundant; Although leisure activities are rich and colorful, the types of common (popular) leisure activities are relatively monotonous, relying heavily on the Internet and computers, and the number of skilled and intellectual types is relatively small; The majority enjoy static mental activities and entertainment, while minority enjoy dynamic physical activities; Most students take a simple rest, while few engage in hobbies, audio-visual activities and sports.

84.24% of college students lack leisure flow experience. Hobbies, audiovisual activities and sports are more likely to produce fluency experience, but fewer college students are engaged in these three types of activities, and fewer of them have experienced leisure flow experience, which is consistent with Tian Xianhua's research results [14]. It is suggested that although most college students participate in leisure activities every day, their leisure activities are not effective. They can only be said to "relax" or "kill time", which fails to make them

devote themselves to leisure activities and really fall in love with this activity. It can be seen from Table 4 that there are a variety of leisure activities for college students to choose from. It can be said that college students with each ability level, each personality characteristic or each interest tendency can find leisure activities that match their own. Therefore, college students generally lack leisure flow experience, which is not because they can't find leisure activities suitable for themselves. Is it because they lack knowledge of various leisure activities and do not grasp the essentials of leisure, or because stress (such as economic stress, learning stress or interpersonal stress) is too heavy to concentrate on leisure activities? This problem needs to be solved through follow-up research.

Boys' leisure flow experience is better than girls', consistent with the results of previous literature [14]. Due to the physical condition, social status, economic ability, rights and responsibilities, space perception, value orientation and social role of both sexes, they have different leisure behaviors and different leisure flow experience. This has been confirmed in a large number of studies on adult leisure [16-19]. This study confirmed that gender differences in leisure have appeared in college period. The reasons are different from adults, mainly due to gender roles, which are shown in the following aspects: (1) Boys enjoy higher social tolerance. Influenced by traditional social roles such as "valuing men over women", "men dominate the world and women dominate the family", the society gives boys higher leisure tolerance, supports and encourages their leisure behavior. Boys also take their leisure behavior for granted, and have no scruples in leisure. However, the more and more enjoyable leisure activities of girls are easy to make people feel "improper", "lazy and playful" and "dissolute", It makes it difficult for girls to put down their scruples in leisure. They often "walk through", shrink their hands and feet, attempt half-heartedly, and can not concentrate on leisure, and it is more difficult to produce a flow experience. (2) Leisure motivation is different. Boys tend to combine leisure and learning, and leisure and learning promote each other. The so-called "learning by playing, playing by learning", leisure causes little waste of time. While girls tend to separate leisure from learning. Leisure causes a large waste of time, which makes them have a contradictory attitude towards leisure: they want to relax, but worry about spending time, and regret not playing easily. (3) Different personalities. Boys have higher emotional stability, stronger anti-interference ability and higher leisure immersion. (4) The opportunities and contents of leisure are different. Due to the stronger physical structure and higher social tolerance, the society provides more leisure opportunities and a wide range of more difficult and avantgarde leisure items for boys, which can give them a full range of strong sensory stimulation and trigger "High" flow experience. Girls' leisure items are less and more gentle, mostly static, and the sensory stimulation is weak, which is not easy to trigger "High" flow experience. (5) Leisure skills are different. Boys are more likely to improve their leisure skills through self-study, participation in training classes, and exchanges with peers, and their leisure activities are more effective and have a higher sense of fluency.

The leisure flow experience of only-child students is higher than that of non-only-child students, which is reflected in the total score and dimension score of LFEQ and consistent with previous research [11]. It suggests that family living conditions and parenting styles have a profound impact on children's behavior. On one hand, only-child students enjoy better leisure resources. Most of the only-children have better economic control

authority and more independent personality. They also pay more attention to interest, enjoyment and the quality of life. In the case of better economic conditions and more leisure time, they have more opportunities to participate in leisure, learn leisure related skills such as participating in various training courses, hiring personal coaches, etc., master more and more systematic leisure essentials, thus completing leisure activities better, and getting more fun and smooth experience; On the other hand, college students have great learning stress and need strong perseverance and will. Because of being spoiled, only-children tend to form a personality that is afraid of hardship, tired and poor in stress resistance, and are not good at actively and reasonably coping with learning pressure, so they turn to leisure activities, reduce stress by indulging in leisure activities, and gradually rely on the smooth experience of leisure. From this perspective, the higher leisure smooth experience of only-children students has its negative connotation.

The higher the academic performance ranking is, the higher the leisure flow experience is, consistent with previous research [13]. There may be the following reasons: (1) Those with good academic achievements are more able to concentrate on activities, which is easy to trigger leisure flow experience. (2) Those with good academic achievements tend to study attentively and nervously. This tension is in sharp contrast to the relaxation in leisure, which makes them more appreciate the fun of leisure. (3) Good results will bring people positive emotions and higher self-confidence, make leisure activities more smooth, and then promote the occurrence of flow experience. (4) Those with good academic achievements are better at combining leisure and learning, and leisure and learning promote each other. The so-called "learning by playing, playing by learning", leisure will not cause a waste of time, but improve the utilization of time; Those with poor academic performance lack this ability, and leisure will cause a waste of time. Therefore, they are easy to take the burden of thinking to participate in leisure activities, and it is difficult to experience the fun.

From the perspective of major category, students majoring in sports and art have the highest leisure fluency experience, which is consistent with previous research [13]. It suggests that leisure skills can promote leisure fluency. Through major study, students majoring in sports and art have mastered relatively correct and systematic movement and activity skills, which promote the effect of leisure due to the effect of "migration", and often get more praise for it, thus triggering "leisure flow experience".

From the perspective of school category, students in comprehensive colleges and universities have the highest scores of leisure fluency experience, while those in colleges such as science and engineering have lower scores, which is consistent with the results of previous studies [11-12]. It is suggested that the combination of multi-disciplinary and multi-professional education may be more conducive to the overall development of students. Generally speaking, comprehensive colleges and universities pay more attention to improving the comprehensive quality of students through leisure education. They are committed to carrying out colorful leisure activities to keep students enthusiastic about leisure and not tired of it. At the same time, they organically integrate the characteristics and resources of various majors, so that students can appreciate the styles and advantages of other departments and majors from leisure activities, absorb the nutrition (such as knowledge, skills, etc.), and promote their comprehensive development. As a result, students can better understand the role and fun of leisure and produce more leisure and flow experience.

The father's occupation is negatively correlated with the total score of LFEQ, and the mother's occupation is positively correlated with the total score of LFEQ, which prompt the father's or mother's occupation affects children's behavior through different mechanisms. As mentioned above, with the society giving more tolerance, support and encouragement to men, men's leisure activities are increasing, and there is even a trend of excessive leisure. The so-called "first class men don't go home after work". Their companionship, care and instruction to children are gradually reduced, including guidance to children's leisure activities [20]. In this way, when the time limit of the father's occupation is high (that is, less free time, such as journalism, real estate, tourism and transportation, manufacturing and education), fathers' time to participate in family education will be less, and the children's leisure literacy from the father will be less and more fragmented, and they will be more difficult to obtain leisure fun and leisure fluency. The situation of mother is different, because family and children are the core of mothers' life. No matter what occupations mothers are engaged in, they will spend their spare time as much as possible to take care of and accompany their children. Mothers who are engaged in journalism, real estate, tourism, transportation, manufacturing, and education are more able to correctly understand the role of leisure and talent due to their work requirements. They will pay more attention to the cultivation of children's leisure literacy, and can promote the formation of children's talent by improving their leisure interest, fun and participation.

The leisure time length on weekdays is positively correlated with the total score of LFEQ, but there is no significant correlation between the leisure time length on weekends and the total score of LFEQ, which is inconsistent with the results of previous studies [21]. It shows that after a fairly intense period of study, a long and sufficient leisure can make students completely relax and immerse, and lead to a flow experience of leisure. The specific reasons need further study.

Taking exploratory tourism as a primary leisure activity positively predict leisure fluency experience, while leisure loitering (including online and below-the-line loitering) negatively predicts leisure fluency experience, which is consistent with previous research results [7, 22]. It suggests the impact of the need for self-realization on the smooth experience of leisure [23]. Serious and intellectual leisure activities can help individuals produce a sense of efficacy and achievement, and improve their leisure fluency experience, while simple time killing can easily make people feel incompetent and bored, and hinder the production of leisure fluency experience.

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